

CIRCULOOS

You can now apply to the
CIRCULOOS Expression of Interest!

What is it?

CIRCULOOS Expression of Interest (EOI) engages supply chain actors in manufacturing industries (e.g., metal, construction, electrical, furniture) to create **Innovative Circular Supply Chains**. Participants will adopt circular practices like refurbishing, remanufacturing, and repurposing, collaborating regionally to enhance circularity.

Apply now!

Benefits

Matchmaking services, webinars and information for a high quality proposal

Adopt emerging and AI tools for secure data sharing, collaboration and value chain optimisation

Funding up to **240K€/team** in Open Calls #2 and #3

Be part of the European Hub for Circularity

Extend product lifespans and minimise waste & pioneer in Circularity

MSMEs become equal member of circular manufacturing value chains

How to apply

Scan the QR to apply!

Upcoming CIRCULOOS Open Calls

The CIRCULOOS Expression Of Interest serves as the first step in a three-step process, facilitating access to funding and scaling opportunities through the project's upcoming **Open Calls #2 and #3** in 2025/2026.

2

Demonstrators (EXDs)

3

Value-chain Extension & Scale-up

